

A systematic review of the vertical integration of the basic sciences in teaching and learning in the clinical years of medical education

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Review question

How effective are educational interventions for teaching or reteaching the basic sciences to clinical year medical students?

Searches

OVID MEDLINE, Embase, PubMed, Web of Science, ERIC. Search dates between 1946 and 2020. Restricted to English language publications.

Types of study to be included

No restrictions on the types of study design or study types eligible for inclusion

Condition or domain being studied

Consolidation of basic science competencies by clinical year medical students

Participants/population

Clinical year medical students.

- Exclude studies involving ONLY medical students in the preclinical years of the medical curriculum.
- Include combinations of preclinical AND clinical medical students in studies.

Intervention(s), exposure(s)

Teaching or reteaching of basic sciences during the clinical years of medical school.

Comparator(s)/control

Standard medical curricula where no review of basic sciences is carried out in the clinical years

Context

Clinical year medical education

Main outcome(s)

Characterisation of the effectiveness of application of vertical integration of the basic sciences in the clinical years of medical education - examining the reasons for success or failure of specific interventions and elucidating the key features of successful interventions.

* Measures of effect

The findings of this review will elucidate the utility of educational interventions aimed at effective subject/disciplinary integration in medical education and thus facilitate the development of a clearer understanding of which approaches are deemed more effective in producing safer and more competent

doctors.

Additional outcome(s)

None

* Measures of effect

Not applicable

Data extraction (selection and coding)

1. Study Characteristics:

Collect baseline study characteristics - Reference, Purpose, Basic science, Theoretical Framework, Geographical location, Source of sample, Sample demographics.

Methods: Data collection Analysis

2. Qualitative Data Analysis:

Direct Quotes

Based on Braun and Clarke's 6-step process.

Data extraction & familiarisation - Collecting quotes from the individual articles. Identify specific recurring patterns. 3 researchers independently perform multiple read-throughs of data

Generation of preliminary codes - Use NVivo, generate initial codes through repeated interrogation of data. Assign codes liberally & exhaustively to group similar data and repeating patterns. Perform constant comparative analysis of all data across all data as new codes are generated. Performed independently by 3 researchers.

Generation of preliminary themes - Codes transformed into themes and sub-themes that determine interaction and overlap of data patterns. Determine thematic hierarchy and produce thematic map. 3 researchers share, combine and challenge each other's results.

Theme review - Review initial themes and interactions and redefine as necessary to ensure all data pieces fit. Review validity of the thematic map. Performed by 3 researchers in discussion

Defining themes - 3 researchers redefine the different themes and sub-themes

Produce report - 3 researchers

Likert Data

Extract Likert scales

Interpret and critique use/analysis

Narrative analysis.

Quantitative Data Analysis:

Data extraction

Collect assessment data from each study

Interpretation, critique & descriptive analysis

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

Quality assessment using:

- The Medical Education Research Study Quality Instrument (MERSQI)
- The Newcastle Ottawa Scale Education (NOS-E)

Strategy for data synthesis

This is primarily a qualitative (narrative) synthesis, with some scope for a meta-analysis depending on the nature of studies included. The nature of the types of education interventions and educational research in medical education means that there is likely to be a heterogeneous mix of studies including qualitative, quantitative and mixed-methods studies. A narrative synthesis of the data is, therefore, more appropriate than a meta-analysis.

A narrative synthesis is also important given that the review aims to investigate how and why certain education interventions for the vertical integration of basic sciences work better than others. Studies will be grouped by type of intervention and outcome of success. The data will be thematically analyzed to foreground any similarities between studies and to elucidate the implications of heterogeneous studies. Three researchers will be involved in the study. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

None

Contact details for further information

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Organisational affiliation of the review

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Review team members and their organisational affiliations

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Type and method of review

Narrative synthesis, Systematic review

Anticipated or actual start date

12 February 2020

Anticipated completion date

31 August 2020

Funding sources/sponsors

None

Conflicts of interest

Language

English

Country

England

Stage of review

Review Ongoing

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

MeSH headings have not been applied to this record

Date of registration in PROSPERO

28 April 2020

Date of first submission

23 March 2020

Stage of review at time of this submission

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	No
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	No
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	No	No
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	No	No

The record owner confirms that the information they have supplied for this submission is accurate and complete and they understand that deliberate provision of inaccurate information or omission of data may be construed as scientific misconduct.

The record owner confirms that they will update the status of the review when it is completed and will add publication details in due course.

Versions

28 April 2020

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